

Client Selection and Resource Allocation via Graph Neural Networks for Efficient Federated Learning in Healthcare Environments

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ABSTRACT

Two of the most significant challenges in decentralized federated learning are resource allocation and client selection. In order to address certain aspects of these challenges, in this paper we introduce a novel approach based on graph neural networks (GNNs). In the present work, we aim to ensure differential privacy guarantees in optimal client selection and resource allocation. Our comparative analysis against two baseline schemes reveals that our solution maintains a relatively low total delay, even as the number of clients increases. Furthermore, our preliminary results indicate that GNNs contribute to differentially private client selection and resource allocation in federated learning, especially in healthcare environments.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Security and privacy → Systems security; • Computing methodologies → Machine learning.

KEYWORDS

resource allocation, federated learning, client selection, differential privacy, networked medical devices

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1 INTRODUCTION

Federated Learning (FL) is a distributed learning paradigm where machine learning models are trained on devices without any kind of raw data exchange between the devices and the server [16]. In this paradigm, training is an act of collaboration between multiple clients, such as research institutions, providing a certain degree of user-level privacy. The FL components are used for the scalability of machine learning applications, ensuring personal data are kept safe at the edge. In this context, fast learning schemes have been proposed in the literature, including [7] and [13]. Decentralized federated learning (DFL) operates on decentralized model exchange between clients, offering resilience to single-point failures and reducing network congestion through direct device-to-device (D2D) communications. Despite these advantages, DFL faces several challenges, including long delays due to frequent decentralized model updates, potentially increasing communication and computation resource usage. Heterogeneity among devices and the decentralized structure may result in stragglers with slower updates, reducing aggregation frequency and impacting convergence rates. In addition, mobility introduces variability in D2D network topology, contributing to extended training times [2].

In the context of medical devices, FL can be used to train lightweight machine learning models on data generated by a large number of devices. Each device contributes its data to the training process, allowing the model to learn from a diverse range of patient populations and clinical scenarios. In addition, it may also help address challenges related to data heterogeneity, as medical devices may generate data with varying characteristics and formats.

Differential privacy (DP) is a technique used to protect the privacy of individuals in large datasets by adding random noise to the data, in such a way that statistical analysis of the data remains accurate without revealing the identity of individual data points. This technique is particularly useful in healthcare and medical devices, where sensitive information about individuals' health and medical conditions is often collected, analyzed and protected from being accessed by unauthorized third parties [8]. DP is essential in FL applications to protect individual data, build user trust, and comply with privacy regulations. By adding controlled noise to

the learning process, it protects against membership inference and re-identification attacks, making it more challenging for adversaries to extract sensitive information. This privacy-preserving framework ensures a balance between model utility and user privacy, encouraging broader participation in federated learning while future-proofing against evolving privacy concerns.

2 RELATED WORK

In [3], the authors highlight the significance of distributed learning in next-generation intelligent networks, emphasizing collaborative model training among intelligent agents without centralized raw data processing for privacy preservation. However, it highlights the challenge of high communication overhead in wireless systems with limited resources, prompting the need for communication-efficient distributed learning algorithms. The study [1] addresses resource efficiency in federated learning through intelligent participant selection and incorporating updates from straggling participants, resulting in improved model quality and optimized resource utilization, thus enhancing the effectiveness of the training process. In [4], the authors provide a comprehensive study of training FL algorithms in realistic wireless network scenarios. They solve the joint optimization problem involving learning, wireless resource allocation, and user selection. The authors of [5] propose FEDACS, a novel personalized FL algorithm that introduces an attention-based client selection mechanism to mitigate challenges arising from non-IID data and data scarcity by prioritizing collaboration among clients with similar data distributions.

In [10], the authors introduce a graph neural network (GNN) designed to enhance bandwidth allocations for multiple legitimate wireless users transmitting to a base station in the presence of an eavesdropper. Furthermore, the authors of [15] introduce a GNN-based approach for DFL in D2D wireless networks, aiming to minimize total training delay and enhance learning performance. The proposed method employs a multi-head graph attention mechanism to capture diverse client and channel features and incorporates a neighbor selection module for clients to choose participating neighbors in model aggregation. To the same extent, the study of [11] proposes a solution to the challenges of dynamic bandwidth allocation in wireless vehicular networks, addressing mobility and heterogeneity with the first algorithm employing GNNs to predict vehicular network connection topology, prioritizing vehicles for bandwidth allocation based on Quality of Service (QoS) requirements and proximity.

DP deployment in FL environments has already been documented in the recent literature. Specifically, the authors of [19] introduce a solution to privacy concerns arising in FL by incorporating the concept of user-level differential privacy. In [20], the authors address the challenge of minimizing FL training delay over wireless channels while considering imbalanced data distributions, privacy constraints, and transmission quality. The study of [9] introduces an iterative DP algorithm for client selection in FL, addressing scenarios where clients coordinate with a central server to complete tasks while deciding to participate based on local computation and probabilistic intent. The algorithm does not rely on client-to-client information exchange and ensures near-optimal values to clients

over long-term average participation with a certain differential privacy guarantee. Following a different approach, the authors of [21] present a novel DP-enhanced FL platform that treats privacy as a resource and addresses the challenge of accumulating privacy leakage in multiple FL jobs. In [22], the authors propose a unified federated learning framework that integrates both horizontal and vertical federated learning approaches. The framework aims to balance privacy preservation, model utility, and system efficiency, crucial for large-scale model training and deployment. The paper formulates and quantifies trade-offs between privacy leakage, utility loss, and efficiency reduction.

In the present study, we present a GNN-based approach that jointly provides optimal resource allocation and client selection with DP guarantees. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that provides a GNN solution considering all three aspects that emerge in DFL environments. Our paper is further organized as follows: in Section 3 we proceed with our system model and the corresponding problem formulation, in Section 4 we present our suggested solution for the joint resource allocation and client selection with DP guarantees, in Section 5 we demonstrate the feasibility and performance of our solution, and in Section 6 we give our concluding remarks.

3 SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a D2D wireless network with N clients in a given area. The DFL process iterates for R training rounds. Considering the potential mobility of the clients, we model the network as a time-varying graph, namely $G_r(V, E_r)$, where V and E_r denote the set of clients (nodes) and the set of communication links (edges) between nodes in the r -th training round, respectively. We assume that clients can move freely at the end of each training round. There is a communication link between two clients when their signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) is greater than or equal to a threshold Ω [15]. We define A_r as the adjacency matrix in the r -th training round with $a_{i,j}^r \in \{0, 1\}$ denoting the existence or not of a link between a client i and a client j . The set of the neighboring nodes of a client i in the r -th training round is defined as \mathcal{N}_i^r . Each client has a local dataset \mathcal{D}_i with D_i data samples. Let parameters $\theta_i^R \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denote the local model of client i after R training rounds. The loss function of the local model of client i , denoted by F_i , is defined as in [15], namely,

$$F_i(\theta_i^R) = \frac{1}{D_i} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{D}_i} \lambda(z; \theta_i^R), \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda(z; \theta_i^R)$ denotes the loss on data sample $z \in \mathcal{D}_i$ with model θ_i^R .

In the r -th training round, client i trains its model locally with K stochastic gradient descent (SGD) steps. We define client i 's model at the κ -th step as $\theta_i^{r,\kappa}$, $1 \leq \kappa \leq K$. It is updated as follows [10]:

$$\theta_i^{r,\kappa} = \theta_i^{r,\kappa-1} - \eta^r \nabla F_i(\theta_i^{r,\kappa-1}), \quad (2)$$

where η^r and $\nabla F_i(\theta_i^{r,\kappa-1})$ denote the learning rate and the gradient of the loss function of client i at the $(\kappa - 1)$ -th SGD step in the r -th training round, respectively. In this work, each client selects a subset of its neighboring client devices to participate in model

aggregation. We define the neighbor selection decision as $s_{i,j}^r \in \{0, 1\}$ which satisfies $s_{i,j}^r \leq a_{i,j}^r$, $i, j \in V$. The neighbor selection matrix for aggregation in the r -th training round is $S^r \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, with $s_i^r \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N}$ denoting the neighbor selection row vector of the client i . We define the set of neighbors that client i has selected for aggregation in the r -th training round as \hat{N}_i^r that includes the non-zero elements in vector s_i^r . Client i updates its local model by aggregating the local models of its selected neighbors in the r -th training round as follows:

$$\theta_i^{r+1}(s_i^r) = \sum_{j \in \hat{N}_i^r} p_{j,i}^r \theta_j^{r,K}, \quad p_{j,i}^r = \frac{D_j}{\sum_{n \in \hat{N}_i^r} D_n}, \quad (3)$$

where $p_{j,i}^r$ represents the weight of the model of client j , when client i performs aggregation at the end of r -th training round. θ_i^{r+1} will then be used as the client i 's model for local training in the $(r+1)$ -th training round.

In DFL, each client needs to select its neighbors, CPU frequency, and transmit power. The chosen values affect the computation delay and communication delay. The computation delay of a client is the time that the client uses for local training. We denote the CPU frequency of client i with the variable $f_i^r \in [f_i^{\min}, f_i^{\max}]$ where f_i^{\min} and f_i^{\max} are the minimum and the maximum CPU frequency of the client i , respectively. Considering that c_i denotes the number of CPU cycles of the client i to process one bit of data and m_i denotes the size of the dataset \mathcal{D}_i , the computation delay is defined as

$$T_i^{c,r} = \frac{c_i m_i K}{f_i^r}. \quad (4)$$

In terms of communication delays, we define the transmit power of client i in the r -th training round as $p_i^r \in [0, p_i^{\max}]$ with p_i^{\max} denoting the maximum transmit power of client i . Let $g_{i,j}^r$ denote the channel gain from client i to client j in the r -th training round. At time t , we define the set of clients that transmit their updated models as $\mathcal{M}(t) \subset V$. The corresponding achievable data rate at time instant t in the r -th training round is defined as:

$$R_{i,j}^r(t) = B \log_2 \left\{ 1 + \frac{p_i^r g_{i,j}^r(t)}{\sum_{\kappa \in \mathcal{M}(t)} |g_{\kappa,j}^r|^2 p_\kappa^r + \sigma^2} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where σ is the received noise power. Consequently, if we denote the communication delay by $T_{j,i}^{t,r}$, then, considering the different transmit power and channel gains of the selected clients and the changing inference over time, the delay is such that:

$$\int_{t^r}^{t^r + T_{j,i}^{t,r}} R_{i,j}^r(t) dt = \xi_m, \quad (6)$$

where t^r denotes the time that the client i receives the model from client j and ξ_m denotes the model size. Finally, $T_i^{t,r} = \max_{j \in \hat{N}_i^r} T_{j,i}^{t,r}$ will be the total time the client i needs to receive the models from its selected neighbors. The total delay of the r -th training round is then presented as the sum of the maximum values of communication and computation delays that are a function of the neighbor selection matrix, transmit power and CPU frequency of all clients.

$$T^r = \max_{i \in V} \{T_i^{c,r} + T_i^{t,r}\}. \quad (7)$$

Due to time-varying topologies, the neighbor selection and resource allocation decisions are independent across training rounds. Here we define as d_{max} the maximal interval of each communication round, which is used to avoid an endless waiting time caused by possible stragglers. The time that the clients with available channels require to jointly complete an update of their respective FL models at r -th communication round, is given by

$$d(r) = \max_{i \in V} \{\min\{T^r, d_{max}\}\}. \quad (8)$$

From the DP point of view, a DP mechanism with parameters ϵ and δ provides a strong criterion for the privacy preservation of distributed data processing systems. In our study, $\epsilon > 0$ is a bound on all outputs on neighboring datasets, namely x and x' , while δ represents the probability of the event that the ratio of the probabilities for the two adjacent datasets cannot be bounded by e^ϵ after adding a privacy-preserving mechanism. We apply the local differential privacy (LDP) [18] where a perturbation mechanism \mathcal{P}_i is applied to each user's dataset independently. We adopt the Gaussian mechanism that has been widely used in the privacy-preserving SGD algorithms and it can satisfy LDP for the r -th client when we properly select the value of the standard deviation (STD) σ_i for each client [19]. Due to the varying channel, the unknown interference and the stochastic scheduling scheme, the exposure time for each client cannot be obtained in advance. Therefore, we only consider the LDP for each client in each communication round. Based on [12], the selected composition of leakage $\hat{\epsilon}_i$ based on the local privacy leakage is

$$\hat{\epsilon}_i = \sqrt{\frac{E_i \ln\left(\frac{1}{\delta_i}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{2}{\delta_i}\right)}} \epsilon_i, \quad (9)$$

where E_i is the times of the model uploading for the r -th client and can be obtained at each communication round. Thus, it is crucial to control the largest delay among all clients. Having defined the system model, the next step is to design the dynamic channel assigning mechanisms in this work to minimize the time delay while completing the training. The problem is formulated as follows:

$$\min_{s_i^r \in S^r} \sum_{r \in R} d(r), \quad (10a)$$

subject to:

$$s_{i,j}^r \leq a_{i,j}^r, \quad i, j \in V, \quad (10b)$$

$$0 \leq p_i^r \leq p_i^{\max}, \quad i \in V, \quad (10c)$$

$$f_i^{\min} \leq f_i^r \leq f_i^{\max}, \quad i \in V, \quad (10d)$$

$$\limsup_{r \in R} \frac{1}{R} \sum_r \mathbb{I}_{i,j}(r) \geq \beta_i, \quad (10e)$$

where β_i is the participating ratio for the i client determined by its DP requirement (ϵ_i, δ_i) [20] and local training model and $\mathbb{I}_{i,j}(r)$ denotes an indicator function which means whether the local training model of client j successfully received by client i at the r -th training round. From Eq. (10a), we deduce that the time used for the update of the local models is determined by the neighboring

selection matrix $s_{i,j}^r$. It is worth mentioning that even if a minimum positive ϵ_i is considered, there are certain effects of these values in the local model training of the clients [20].

4 GRAPH NEURAL NETWORKS FOR CLIENT SELECTION AND RESOURCE ALLOCATION

For the purposes of our study, we propose a multi-head graph attention network (GAT) [17]. The attention mechanism can help each client learn the features of its neighboring clients and determine their importance score for selection. Our algorithm consists of an encoder, a selection features network and a decoder. In order to capture the intrinsic properties of the D2D networks, the encoder encodes client features, including maximum transmit power, maximum and minimum CPU frequencies and differential privacy budget, and edge features that represent channel gains. The neighboring selection network determines the set of neighboring clients for model aggregation. The decoder determines the final allocation decisions of the selected clients. Let $x_i^{f,r} = (p_i^{max}, f_i^{min}, f_i^{max}, \epsilon_i^{min}) \in \mathbb{R}^4$ denote the feature vector of client i . Similarly, the edge feature, denoted by $x^{e,r}$, represents the absolute value of the channel gain of link (i, j) .

4.1 Encoder and Selection Features

We consider both node and edge features. Node features represent communication and computation capabilities of devices. Edge features characterize the channel gain which affects the communication delay. The client encoder utilizes these two features to capture the intrinsic properties of the network topology. We use the z-score normalization to stabilize the gradients of GNN. Since each client aggregates features of different magnitudes from its neighbors, local normalization is applied in order to ensure that the mean and standard deviation of the features are zero and one, respectively [15]. In this work, we deploy long short-term memory (LSTM) as the encoder for the features of the clients. The features of client i at the training round r , denoted by $r_r^{(i)}$, are defined as:

$$r_r^{(i)} = \text{LSTM} \left(x_i^{f,r} \right). \quad (11)$$

The features of all clients will then be gathered as a set, denoted by \mathcal{R}_r , namely,

$$\mathcal{R}_r = \left\{ r_r^{(i)}, \dots, r_r^{(N)} \right\}. \quad (12)$$

Furthermore, we denote by \mathcal{S}_r the selection decisions of the clients, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{S}_r = \left\{ s_r^{(0)}, s_r^{(1)}, \dots, s_r^{(N)} \right\}, \quad (13)$$

where $s_r^{(i)}$ represents the selection feature of agent i at the training round r . Our GAT-based algorithm models the features of all clients simultaneously, in the sense that:

$$\mathcal{S}_r = \text{GAT}(\mathcal{R}_r, E_r), \quad (14)$$

where E_r represents the set that contains the edge features at the training round r .

We proceed with the process of neighboring selection, by considering the client features \mathcal{R}_r , defined in equation (12). The selection

representation occurs via a GNN that handles all nodes, edges, and continuous edge features. By aggregating information from neighborhoods, several GAT layers are employed with each layer updating node features, denoted by h_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. A layer first transforms node and edge features accordingly, and then it aggregates neighboring node features with a multi-head attention mechanism. This combination allows the GAT layers to capture dependencies between nodes. GAT gives updated node features based on the information received by its neighborhood. A concatenated feature vector, e_{ij}^r , defined by

$$e_{ij}^r = [e_{ij}][h_i][h_j], \quad (15)$$

represents the edge feature of node j from node i 's point of view, which is then forwarded to a shared attention mechanism. The attention mechanism \mathbf{a}^T is a single-layer, feed-forward neural network with LeakyRelu, softmax linearization, and non-linearity attributes. Its attention coefficients, a_{ij} , indicate the importance of the node j to node i . Then, we compute the node attention scores to generate the node embeddings.

$$a_{ij} = \frac{\exp \left(\text{LeakyReLU} \left(\mathbf{a}^T [h_i] [e_{ij}^r] \right) \right)}{\sum_{k \in \widehat{N}_i} \exp \left(\text{LeakyReLU} \left(\mathbf{a}^T [h_i] [e_{ik}^r] \right) \right)}. \quad (16)$$

We implement independent attention mechanisms per node. Specifically, the multi-head attention mechanism is shaped by $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ independent attention mechanisms with their features to be concatenated, resulting in the following output feature representation:

$$h_i^{new} = \sigma \left(\sum_{j \in \widehat{N}_i} \left[a_{ij}^1 W_h^1 e_{ij}^r \right] \left[a_{ij}^2 W_h^2 e_{ij}^r \right] \dots \left[a_{ij}^K W_h^K e_{ij}^r \right] \right), \quad (17)$$

with σ , W_h and k representing the sigmoid function, the weighted sum of node features over its neighborhood, and the number of attention heads, respectively. When performing training in DFL, the full participation scheme may incur high communication delays. Thus, we propose a neighbor selection module to determine which neighbors to be selected for each client. The inputs to the module consist of the concatenated embedding of a client and the embeddings of its neighbors. The concatenated embedding of client i and its neighbor j is $h_{i,j}^{new,r} = [h_i^{new,r}][h_j^{new,r}]$. We apply a decoder for the neighboring selection decisions and the resource allocation matrix. For each neighboring client $j \in \widehat{N}_i^r$, client i determines the selection decision $s_{i,j}$ based on a pre-defined threshold $\gamma \in (0, 1)$. Since bi-directional model exchanges are required for model aggregation in DFL, we require

$$e_{i,j}^r \geq \gamma, \quad e_{j,i}^r \geq \gamma. \quad (18)$$

4.2 Decoder

We deploy an LSTM decoder as:

$$f_r^{(i)} = \text{LSTM} \left(\left[r_r^{(i)} \right] \left[s_r^{(i)} \right] \right), \quad (19)$$

Figure 1: Comparison of the total delay on training versus the number of clients.

with $[r_r^{(i)}][s_r^{(i)}]$ representing the concatenation of the corresponding features and f_r gives the selection features of the nodes. The outcome includes only the features of the selected nodes for resource allocation. We further employ a full graph neural network block containing a global block, a node block, and an edge block. Adopting a set-to-set mapping approach similar to [6], we define the resource allocation GNN, denoted by RAG, as:

$$\text{RAG} = \{Q_{enc}^u, Q_{enc}^e, Q_{dec}^u\}, \quad (20)$$

where we adopted the following notation: $Q_{enc}^u: \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ represents the encoding rates of the node features (transmit power, CPU frequencies, privacy constraints), $Q_{enc}^e: \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_e}$ the encoding rates of the channel gains between the clients, $Q_{dec}^u: \mathbb{R}^{n_u} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the decoding of the final state for the assignment of resources, and $(Q^e, Q^u, Q^b): \mathbb{R}^{n_u+n_e+n_b} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_e}, \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ or \mathbb{R}^{n_b} represent the updates of the graph's edges, nodes, and global values, respectively. Furthermore, n_u, n_e and n_b denote the hyperparameters that represent the size of the node encodings, the edges and the final resource assignments, respectively.

We define the loss function as a weighted sum of the delay, as highlighted in equations (10). The aggregated compressed parameters of client i in the r -th training round are computed as in [15], namely,

$$x_i^{p,r+1}(s_i^r) = \sum_{j \in \tilde{N}_i^r} \rho_{j,i}^r x_j^{p,r}. \quad (21)$$

To ensure that the proposed algorithm can adapt to different network settings, we train our GNN in an offline and unsupervised manner. We generate a set of D2D network scenarios with topology changes and time-varying channel conditions. Due to the small size of the neighbors' node features, compressed model parameters, and channel conditions, each client collects these features in each scenario with negligible communication delay. It then determines the decision and sends the decision to its neighbors and the loss of each client can be calculated.

5 RESULTS

We consider a scenario with randomly located clients in a 5×5 km² area. We assume that each client can arbitrarily move in any direction. Let the moving distance between two training rounds rely on uniform distribution $[0, 100]$ m. We consider the transit power of each device to follow a uniform distribution $[8, 15]$ mW. Regarding the frequency of each client device, we set it as $f_i^{min} = [0.1, 0.2]$ GHz and $f_i^{max} = [1.5, 2.5]$ GHz. The privacy budget values are considered to be the same for every client with $e_i = [0.25, 0.5, 1]$ for the evaluation of trade-offs between training loss and privacy strength. We initialize the transmit power and CPU frequency of each client to the maximum value and implement our trained GNN. Each client can independently generate their decisions and obtain the delay by recording the wall clock time. Indicatively, we consider scenarios with 20 and 50 clients. We use the Regensburg pediatric appendicitis dataset [14] as the dataset and allocate the same number of data samples to the local dataset of each client in all cases. We adopt the convolutional neural networks with three convolutional layers, two fully connected layers, and a dropout layer in DFL. We compare the performance of our algorithm with the following baseline schemes: (a) Random sampling DFL with neighbors to be randomly selected by each client based on a certain ratio ζ , with $0 < \zeta < 1$. Then, the resources are allocated using our proposed GNN approach, (b) Full participation DFL with each client performing local aggregation based on the model obtained from all of its neighbors. The power and CPU frequencies are allocated to the clients using our pre-trained GNN.

In Fig. 1, we compare the total delay on training of our proposed algorithm with the baselines. We choose $\zeta = 0.5$ for random sampling. When N is equal to 50 our proposed algorithm can achieve a total delay of 116.53% and 75.21% lower than full participation and random sampling, respectively. This indicates the effectiveness of partial participation and that the neighboring clients are properly selected by the proposed algorithm.

In Fig. 2, we show the training loss rate considering three different privacy budgets and two different client numbers. Specifically, we set $\epsilon = 0.25, 0.5, 1$. It shows that our proposed scheme gives better

Figure 2: Training loss of GNN when ϵ changes with $N = 20$ clients and $N = 50$ clients.

convergence results with smaller positive privacy budgets included in the node features of our clients.

6 CONCLUSION

This paper provides a novel and effective solution to the challenges of DFL for healthcare applications. By introducing a GNN-based approach, the study simultaneously addresses optimal client selection, resource allocation, and DP guarantees. Our preliminary results emphasize the importance of incorporating privacy-preserving techniques in federated learning for healthcare environments. Our future work aims to incorporate more sophisticated DP mechanisms in GNN-based FL settings contributing to their increasing privacy-preserving requirements.

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